

////////////////////////////////////

CONFLICT AND CREATIVITY WITHIN DESIGN TEAMS

Tim Haats / Lois Frankel
Carleton University School of Industrial Design
thaats@connect.carleton.ca

ABSTRACT

Organizations are faced with a fast-paced competitive marketplace and rapidly advancing technologies, yielding the need for an innovative response for any hope of survival. This innovative response requires the establishment of diverse, collaborative design teams that can confront the increasing complexities of design. As members collaborate and interact with one another, conflicts arise that have both beneficial and detrimental effects on the creative process. Through a review of extant literature, this paper focuses on the relationship between conflict and creativity, and how cognitive- and affective conflict affect the generation of ideas and the development of design solutions that contribute to innovative outcomes. Cognitive conflict, if experienced at a moderate level, is found to be beneficial for stimulating creativity whereas affective conflict is considered detrimental. In order to enhance creativity during the early conceptual design phase, cognitive conflict between team members must be moderated while preventing the impediment of affective conflict.

Keywords: Conflict, Creativity, Design Teams.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, design has become more of an integrated activity requiring the efforts of multiple individuals to work in teams and to collaborate on design projects (Cross & Cross, 1995). Design today is complex and teams need to foster diversity amongst their members in terms of backgrounds, experience, skills, and knowledge (Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010). This diversity is very important as organizations are faced with rapidly advancing technologies and an increasingly competitive and fast-paced marketplace, resulting in

the need to be creative and to develop innovative products or services (Chen, 2006; Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). Existing knowledge is considered inadequate in supporting this innovative development which means that design teams need to sprout new knowledge that will contribute to creative and innovative thought (Leenders, van Engelen, & Kratzer, 2003). Bringing together team members with different disciplinary knowledge and promoting the sharing of this knowledge is essential for maximizing the creative performance of the design team and for implementing a quality design process (Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010). However, this introduces considerable challenges for effective collaboration (De Dreu & Weingart, 2003). It is inevitable that design teams will experience conflict at some level during a project. A clash of views, interests, goals and values is not uncommon in a group of diverse members (Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010). When studying design teams, it is important to consider the effects of conflict on the team's performance and output. Mooney, Holahan, and Amason (2007) state that conflict "may be at once the most powerful centrifugal and centripetal force with which a team must contend" (p.755).

It is easy to think that conflict would be detrimental to design teams, but much research has found that different types of conflict have different effects on team functioning and that conflict can actually be beneficial (Jehn, 1995). However, studies have also shown that the effects of conflict vary depending on what tasks are being completed and which stage or phase of a project the team is at, meaning that conflict is dynamic throughout the entire design process and is not just a statically occurring event (Chen, 2006; Jehn, 1995). By analyzing the effects of conflict at different phases of the design process,

researchers can gain a better understanding of conflict and how it should be managed within design teams throughout the project life cycle.

Building from the extant literature on conflict and creativity within management and work teams in general, this paper focuses on the early conceptual phase of the design process and how the different types of conflict affect the generation of ideas and the development of design solutions that contribute to innovative outcomes. More specifically, it addresses the relationship between cognitive- and affective conflict and creativity within design teams (Figure 1), both of which are described later in this paper. Based on this literature review, it is proposed that, in order to enhance creativity during the early conceptual design phase, cognitive conflict between team members must be moderated while preventing the impedance of affective conflict.

Figure 1. Cognitive conflict and affective conflict influence creativity within design teams.

BACKGROUND

Conflict in teams has been a popular topic for researchers over many years (Amason, 1996; Amason & Sapienza, 1997; Behfar & Peterson, 2008; Chen, 2006; De Dreu & Weingart, 2003; Jehn, 1995). Most of the research has revolved around work groups and management in organizations and how conflict contributes to the functioning of teams involved in decision-making. For example, Jehn (1995)

examined work groups and management teams and questioned whether conflict can be beneficial. She found that it depended on the type of conflict, whether cognitive or affective, and the structure of the group in terms of task type, task interdependence, and group norms. Amason (1996) assessed the effects of conflict on strategic decision-making in top management teams supporting similar findings that different types of conflict have different effects on decision quality, consensus and affective acceptance.

Building on the foundational research of conflict and work groups, Behfar and Peterson (2008) explored the linkages between strategies for managing the different types of conflict and group performance and satisfaction. Their study provides evidence for effective conflict management and contributes practical information for management teams to implement. Researchers have also looked into the relationship between conflict and innovation in organizations. De Dreu (2006) addressed this relationship by asking whether, when, and why conflict can contribute to innovation in work teams and found that the innovativeness of teams depended on the level of cognitive conflict experienced and that this was mediated by collaborative problem solving.

De Clercq, Thongpapanl, and Dimov (2009) investigated the moderating effect of social capital on the conflict-innovation relationship and found that social interaction and trust have opposing influences. Higher levels of social interaction were found to promote a stronger positive relationship between cognitive conflict and innovation as well as a stronger negative relationship between affective conflict and innovation. On the other hand, higher levels of trust promoted a weaker relationship between cognitive conflict and innovation.

Innovation is often the outcome of a creative process which means that research on creativity and conflict has important implications (Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby, & Herron, 1996). Perry-Smith (2006) studied the role of social relationships in facilitating creativity at the individual level. She explored creativity and social network theories to examine the

effects that relationship strength, network position, and external ties have on individual creativity. Friedrich and Mumford (2009) studied the effects of conflicting information on creative thought and found that the performance of a team depended on various factors of the information presented.

In terms of design, because it has only been considered recently as an important team activity, researchers are beginning to address the effects of conflict within design teams specifically. Once designers began collaborating and working together in groups, social processes in design activity became important to consider as designers were now required to directly communicate and interact with others involved in the project (Cross & Cross, 1995). Kilker (1999) used social identity theory to examine the role that social identities or “design identities” play in influencing conflict within collaborative design teams. Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, and Meijer (2010) analysed how design teams cope with conflict during idea generation and how conflict behaviour styles mediate the creative outcome. Farh, Lee, and Farh (2010) have examined the relationship between conflict, creativity, and project life cycle. Their research proposes that cognitive conflict has a curvilinear effect on team creativity and that this relationship is moderated by the project life cycle. Specifically, they found that the curvilinear effect of cognitive conflict on team creativity is strongest during the early phases of a project in comparison to later phases. Considering these findings, it should be clear that the emphasis of this paper is relevant and appropriate as the study focuses on conflict and creativity at these early phases of the design process. Before discussing the effects conflict has on design teams and creativity, it is important to define what conflict means in this particular context.

CONFLICT

According to the Oxford American Dictionary (Ehrlich, Flexner, Carruth, & Hawkins, 1980), conflict is defined as the “disagreement between people with different ideas or beliefs” (p.133). Another definition of conflict describes it as “the perceived incompatibilities or disagreements among exchange partners” (De Clercq, Thongpapanl, & Dimov, 2009,

p. 283). In both definitions, one of the key ingredients is the requirement for more than one person’s involvement. Another key ingredient is the lack of agreement between those involved. The first definition also includes two important words: ideas and beliefs. An individual’s ideas or beliefs can be relevant to external actions or tasks and to internal, personal feelings. An action or task can refer to the activity being undertaken by a team whether it is sketching, building prototypes, or just discussing ideas. Each member will have their own thoughts and beliefs about what tasks are important and about the outcome of those tasks. Feelings can refer to the social, emotional, or relationship aspects that result from an interaction between two or more parties. Members will have their own personal ideas and beliefs about the others in the team which essentially affects the relationships between them. Because members of design teams contribute through both task and social inputs, these issues need to be considered (De Dreu, 2006). Therefore, in this particular context, conflict refers to the disagreements and tensions of task- and relationship related issues between members of a design team.

Accordingly, this definition can be broken down into two main types: cognitive conflict and affective conflict. Cognitive conflict, also known as task conflict, occurs when there are differences between team members’ judgments, interpretations, ideas or perspectives about the tasks being performed. In the context of design teams, this could include dissents about planning and scheduling of time, the appropriateness of prototyping and testing, and the selection of concept solutions to the design problem. Affective conflict, also known as relationship conflict, arises when there are interpersonal incompatibilities or emotional disputes among team members which are unrelated to the tasks at hand (Jehn, 1995; Amason & Sapienza, 1997). Design teams may experience this in the form of interpreting personal attacks from others based on the ideas, opinions and desires of individual members, which can result from a lack of consensus understanding of the design problem or from differences in approaches to problem solving. The major differences between these two types of conflict are the association with the given task and

the emotional connection that may be involved. Cognitive conflict has a direct association with the task in progress but, has no connection to personal emotions whereas affective conflict does not have a direct association with the task but, is heavily connected with an individual's emotions. Before considering the effects cognitive conflict and affective conflict have on the creativity of design teams, the concept of creativity must also be defined in context.

CREATIVITY

Creativity is a very broad term that can be used to mean something different depending on the context of use. Kaufman (2009) discusses this by asking whether creativity refers to a beautiful piece of artwork or an ingenious computer program, or whether it refers to the sensation of the "a-ha" process when something is figured out or perhaps how a creative person behaves. He supports this point with an analogy of the term "love" which is a word that is often used to describe feelings for one's parents, friends, significant other, or favourite food. The words are appropriately used in each context but, the underlying meanings are something different. The study of creativity is immense and there are many theories that attempt to make sense of the subject (Kaufman, 2009), though, the scope of this paper only requires a basic understanding of the term as it pertains to design and design teams.

Creativity can be referred to as the quality or state of being creative. The Oxford American Dictionary (Ehrlich, Flexner, Carruth, & Hawkins, 1980) defines the term creative as "having the power or ability to create things" and "showing imagination and originality as well as routine skill" (p.137). Based on this definition, creativity can be expressed through a design team's ability to use their creative skills in the development of novel and original things such as products or services. According to Kaufman (2009), the definition of creativity tends to revolve around two factors: (1) it must represent something different, new, or innovative, and (2) it must be appropriate, relevant and useful.

Friedrich and Mumford (2009) also note that it is not sufficient to just generate ideas but, that the

effectiveness of the ideas must be evaluated as well. Their understanding of creativity is referred to as a process of creative thought or problem solving which includes conceptual combination, exploration, idea generation, and idea evaluation. These four elements are not the only elements involved in the creativity process but, they are the most critical for a team's creative problem solving efforts (Friedrich & Mumford, 2009). Conceptual combination refers to the analysis of information and the reorganization of existing knowledge to create new understandings of the design problem. This means that team members need to share available information and their diverse disciplinary knowledge in order to provide a basis for creative thought. Exploration refers to the elaborative activity of assessing implications of the new knowledge and understandings created during conceptual combination. This implies that team members need to establish connections with this new knowledge providing further support for the creativity process. Idea generation is simply the creation of new ideas using the founded knowledge and understanding from conceptual combination and exploration. Team members need to create and share their ideas in an attempt to develop potential concept solutions for the design problem. Finally, the creativity process concludes with idea evaluation in which the thoughts and ideas that surfaced during idea generation are evaluated for quality and effectiveness. The design team needs to assess their ideas in order to create valuable concept solutions.

Creativity is also based on divergent thinking which involves an open scanning of information and associations that allows for disparate things to be pulled together in new ways (Russ, 1993). This is why collaboration in design teams has become so important. Problem solving is another component of creativity (Leenders, van Engelen, & Kratzer, 2003). Design teams must engage in problem solving in order to create innovative solutions to the given design problem. It is important to note that creativity differs from innovation. Innovation is generally the result of a creative process as creativity provides new ideas and innovation depends on the successful implementation of those ideas (Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby, & Herron, 1996).

Creativity is basically the essence of the early conceptual phase of the design process.

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN PHASE

The conceptual phase of the design process is essentially part of the front end of any new project. Specifically, it is implemented after an initial research phase in which information and resources are gathered but, most often tends to occur at random, unknown points during the tail-end of preliminary research. This randomness is characteristic of a process that is driven by non-routine tasks which are those exemplified by complexity and uncertainty, typically involving problem solving with no set procedures and high levels of variability (Jehn, 1995).

Considering the four elements used by Friedrich and Mumford (2009) to establish an understanding of creativity, as was previously mentioned, the conceptual design phase can also be understood through the elements of conceptual combination, exploration, idea generation, and idea evaluation. During this phase, design teams collaborate and exchange knowledge to produce new understandings that are elaborated into relevant insights, which are then utilized to generate ideas and evaluate potential concept solutions for the design problem. Based on this framework, information is already collected prior to the conceptual phase and the final outcome is a design concept (Figure 2). Having established an understanding of creativity and the early conceptual phase of the design process, the

relationship between creativity and conflict can now be examined.

CONFLICT AND CREATIVITY

Conflict can be both beneficial and detrimental to a work team's functioning and performance but, it depends on the type of conflict that is experienced within the group (Jehn, 1995). As noted, much of the research on conflict has found that cognitive- or task conflict is beneficial whereas affective- or relationship conflict is detrimental. Teams experience cognitive conflict when there are disagreements about task-related issues such as the distribution of resources, the utilization of procedures and policies, and the judgments and interpretations of information. On the other hand, teams experience affective conflict when disagreements arise that involve personal tastes, political preferences, individual values, or interpersonal styles (De Dreu, 2006).

Jehn's (1995) work discovered that cognitive conflict is only beneficial towards the team's performance when the team is working together on non-routine tasks. She found that when teams experience cognitive conflict, they tend to discuss task-related issues more openly. This open discussion stimulates critical evaluation of problems and decision options. De Dreu (2006) also argues that cognitive conflict increases the tendency for group members to scrutinize task issues and to process task-relevant information more deeply. Further, opposing points of view amongst team members encourages the

Figure 2. The conceptual design phase.

generation of new ideas and promotes the development of a more complete understanding of the problems and alternative solutions (Chen, 2006). This is particularly important for enhancing creativity during the early conceptual design phase. Design teams need to develop an innovative solution to a specific design problem which requires a deep, collective understanding of the problem-space and the generation of many creative ideas that will encourage critical evaluation of the proposed solutions before delivering the final concept. Creative thought is not an isolated process but, rather, it occurs in the context of other ideas being provided by other members of the team (Friedrich & Mumford, 2009). Therefore, teams should promote a psychologically safe climate early on in the project so that team members feel comfortable in bringing up ideas that may be counter to others (Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). If this team climate is not well established, the group and its members are susceptible to the initiation of affective conflict.

In contrast to the benefits of cognitive conflict, the introduction of affective conflict within teams can create negative emotions and animosity between members and towards the project task which causes detrimental effects on the team's performance and outcome (Jehn 1995; Amason, 1996). According to Parayitam and Dooley (2009), affective conflict is negatively related to decision commitment, implying that teams also experience an inability to make good decisions and to stick with them. These findings about the benefits and detriments of conflict clearly indicate the need to increase cognitive conflict and to simultaneously decrease affective conflict within teams. However, this is problematic because both types of conflict tend to be moderately correlated in the positive direction (De Dreu & Weingart, 2003; Chen, 2006; Mooney, Holahan, & Amason, 2007; Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). This means that the stimulation of one conflict type will often emanate the other.

With this in mind, it seems impossible to control an increase in cognitive conflict without having an increase in affective conflict. The key factor of this correlation is the term "moderate". A meta-analysis conducted by De Dreu and Weingart (2003) pointed

out that there is considerable variation across the studies that have found this positive correlation which ultimately indicates that there are dependents involved in the mediation of the relationship. De Dreu and Weingart (2003) also found support that cognitive conflict and affective conflict are in fact unique constructs suggesting that the prompting of one does not necessarily induce the other. In this case, perhaps it is probable to increase cognitive conflict as much as possible and to find ways that will diminish affective conflict in order to optimize creativity within design teams. Although, research has proven that too much cognitive conflict is actually detrimental (Jehn, 1995; De Dreu & Weingart, 2003; De Dreu, 2006). One explanation for this is that too much cognitive conflict may lead to an inability to perceive, process, and evaluate information, essentially stemming from a mental overload (De Dreu & Weingart, 2003). Design teams may not be able to interpret an excess of information and opinions and can easily lose sight of the project goals resulting in a lack of progress (Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). Thus, as cognitive conflict increases to relatively high levels, information exchange and collaborative problem solving depreciate (De Dreu, 2006). An alternate explanation is that high levels of cognitive conflict may actually turn into affective conflict, depending on certain determinants such as open-mindedness and trust (Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010; Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010). As stated by Mooney, Holahan and Amason (2007), "affective conflict is, in some cases, cognitive conflict gone awry". A study conducted by De Dreu (2006) on the conflict-innovation relationship found that as the measure of cognitive conflict increased to greater levels of intensity, affective conflict was induced and team innovation declined. It was proposed that it may have been the presence of affective conflict instead of the increased levels of cognitive conflict that ceased innovation. In conclusion of his study, De Dreu (2006) reasoned that there is a curvilinear relationship between cognitive conflict and innovation in work teams. This means that teams are more innovative when there is a moderate level of cognitive conflict as compared to low or high levels.

Figure 3. The effects of cognitive- and affective conflict on creativity.

Another finding from De Dreu's (2006) study proposed that this curvilinear relationship is mediated by collaborative problem solving. As mentioned earlier, innovation is often the result of creative thought (Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby, & Herron, 1996) and problem solving is a component of creativity (Leenders, van Engelen, & Kratzer, 2003). Hence, this finding can be used to surmise that a similar curvilinear relationship exists between cognitive conflict and creativity. In fact, research has found that it does exist. Leenders, van Engelen and Kratzer (2003) determined that the amount of information that is exchanged between members of a virtual design team should be kept to a moderate level in order to enhance creativity and innovation. Recent research conducted by Farh, Lee and Farh (2010) has also found that moderate levels of cognitive conflict tend to maximize team creativity. Figure 3 shows this curvilinear relationship which is sometimes referred to as an inverted U-shaped relationship. It also shows the relationship between affective conflict and creativity. As can be seen, enhancing creativity requires moderate levels of cognitive conflict and, at the same time, very low levels of affective conflict. A further finding of Farh, Lee and Farh's (2010) research is that the enhancement of creativity is optimal during the earlier stages of a project life cycle. This is important because it is essential for design teams to harness creativity and creative thought during the early conceptual phase of the design process.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this literature review provide insights into new and developing areas of design research with the potential for further investigation. By looking at the extensive examination of conflict and creativity in the fields of psychology and business management, several questions and hypotheses can be considered in relation to interdisciplinary design practice.

Proposing that design teams must maintain a moderate level of cognitive conflict while preventing the introduction of affective conflict during the early conceptual phase of the design process, is only the starting point for empirical research. Future investigations may explore how this conflict is managed accordingly and whose responsibility it would be to do so. Can this be a designer's role? Ethnographic observation of design teams in action could provide more insight into the specific tasks that contribute to cognitive conflict and the techniques for moderating those tasks effectively. Another potential area of research revolves around team composition, looking at various levels of functional diversity and the optimal number of collaborative team members for leveraging cognitive conflict. Future research may also delve into the differences between creativity, ingenuity, and innovation, dealing with the management of conflict in order to enhance each separately and collectively. Accordingly, this paper opens the door to further

developments in understanding the processes involved in collaborative design initiatives and the effects of team-member interaction.

CONCLUSION

Organizations today are faced with a fast-paced competitive marketplace and rapidly advancing technologies which yield the need for an innovative response for any hope of survival (Chen, 2006; Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). This innovative response requires the establishment of collaborative design teams that can confront the increasing complexities of design. Diversity in experience and knowledge is necessary to foster creativity through the formation of new knowledge and understandings (Leenders, van Engelen, & Kratzer, 2003; Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010).

As members collaborate and interact with one another on design projects, conflicts arise that have both beneficial and detrimental effects on the creative process. Cognitive conflict is beneficial for stimulating creativity as team members engage in critical evaluations allowing for the generation of new ideas and a deeper processing of information (Jehn, 1995; De Dreu, 2006; Chen, 2006) whereas affective conflict is detrimental, providing a platform for members to build animosity towards others and the project resulting in poor performance and a lack of progress (Jehn 1995; Amason, 1996). Although cognitive conflict is known to be beneficial, it can also have detrimental effects if there is too much of it (Jehn, 1995; De Dreu & Weingart, 2003; De Dreu, 2006). High levels of cognitive conflict tend to overload the mental system resulting in an inability to process and evaluate presented information (De Dreu & Weingart, 2003). It also seems that high levels of cognitive conflict actually create affective conflict at which point the negative effects of affective conflict take over (De Dreu, 2006; Mooney, Holahan, & Amason, 2007; Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010; Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, & Meijer, 2010). Accordingly, there is a curvilinear relationship between cognitive conflict and team creativity and this is best established during the early phases of a project (Leenders, van Engelen, & Kratzer, 2003; Farh, Lee, & Farh, 2010). Therefore, it is proposed that cognitive conflict must be

moderated while hindering the effects of affective conflict to optimize creativity during the early conceptual phase of the design process.

REFERENCES

- Amabile, T. M., Conti, R., Coon, H., Lazenby, J., & Herron, M. (1996). Assessing the work environment for creativity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(5), 1154-1184.
- Amason, A. C. (1996). Distinguishing the effects of functional and dysfunctional conflict on strategic decision making: Resolving a paradox for top management teams. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(1), 123-148.
- Amason, A. C., & Sapienza, H. J. (1997). The effects of top management team size and interaction norms on cognitive and affective conflict. *Journal of Management*, 23(4), 495-516.
- Badke-Schaub, Goldschmidt, G., & Meijer, M. (2010). How does cognitive conflict in design teams support the development of creative ideas? *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 19(2), 119-133.
- Behfar, K. J., & Peterson, R. S. (2008). The critical role of conflict resolution in teams: A close look at the links between conflict type, conflict management strategies, and team outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(1), 170-188.
- Chen, M.-H. (2006). Understanding the benefits and detriments of conflict on team creativity process. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 15(1), 105-116.
- Cross, N., & Cross, A. C. (1995). Observations of teamwork and social processes in design. *Design Studies*, 16(2), 143-170.
- De Clercq, D., Thongpapanl, N., & Dimov, D. (2009). When good conflict gets better and bad conflict becomes worse: The role of social capital in the conflict-innovation relationship. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 37, 283-297.
- De Dreu, C. K. (2006). When too little or too much hurts: Evidence for a curvilinear relationship between task conflict and innovation in teams. *Journal of Management*, 32(1), 83-107.
- De Dreu, C. K., & Weingart, L. R. (2003). Task versus relationship conflict, team performance, and team member satisfaction: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(4), 741-749.
- Ehrlich, E., Flexner, S. B., Carruth, G., & Hawkins, J. M. (Eds.). (1980). *Oxford American dictionary*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Farh, J.-L., Lee, C., & Farh, C. I. (2010, August 16). Task conflict and team creativity: A question of how much and when. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 1-8.
- Friedrich, T. L., & Mumford, M. D. (2009). The effects of conflicting information on creative thought: A source of performance improvements or decrements? *Creativity Research Journal*, 21(2), 265-281.
- Jehn, K. A. (1995). A multimethod examination of the benefits and detriments of intragroup conflict. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 40, 256-282.
- Kaufman, J. C. (2009). *Creativity 101*. New York: Springer Publishing Company, LLC.
- Kilker, J. (1999, Fall). Conflict on collaborative design teams: Understanding the role of social identities. *IEEE Technology and Society Magazine*, pp. 12-21.
- Leenders, R. T., van Engelen, J. M., & Kratzer, J. (2003). Virtuality, communication, and new product team creativity: a social network perspective. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 20, 69-92.

Mooney, A. C., Holahan, P. J., & Amason, A. C. (2007). Don't take it personally: Exploring cognitive conflict as a mediator of affective conflict. *Journal of Management Studies*, 44(5), 733-758.

Parayitam, S., & Dooley, R. S. (2009). The interplay between cognitive- and affective conflict and cognition- and affect-based trust in influencing decision outcomes. *Journal of Business Research*, 62, 789-796.

Perry-Smith, J. E. (2006). Social yet creative: The role of social relationships in facilitating individual creativity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(1), 85-101.

Russ, S. W. (1993). *Affect and Creativity: The Role of Affect and Play in the Creative Process*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.